

Management of Student Learning Anxiety through Self-Efficacy during the Pandemic Period

Melda Rumia Rosmery Simorangkir¹, Risma Uly Manalu²,
Hendrikus Male³

¹(Faculty Of Teacher Training and Education, Guidance and Counseling Study Program / Universitas Kristen Indonesia, Indonesia)

²(Faculty Of Teacher Training and Education, Mathematics Study Program / Universitas Kristen Indonesia, Indonesia)

³(Faculty of Letters, English Language Education Study Program / Universitas Kristen Indonesia, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: *This study aims to obtain information about the management of learning anxiety through self-efficacy in students during the pandemic at SMP Mutiara Baru Bekasi. The method used in this study is a qualitative method with the subjects in this study are mathematics teachers and grade IX students of SMP Mutiara Baru Bekasi. The object of this research is the counseling guidance teacher, the data collection techniques used are primary data sources and secondary data sources. Primary data sources include questionnaires, observation, interviews, documentation. The informants of this study were guidance and counseling teachers, while secondary sources were indirect sources that provided data to data collectors through guidance and counseling teachers or in the form of documents. From the results of the research conducted, it was found that the reinforcement and motivation provided by the guidance and counseling teacher in the form of self-efficacy during learning from home rebuilt students' confidence in reducing changes in anxiety that occurred in students when learning from home.*

KEYWORDS-*Anxiety, Pandemic, Self-efficacy*

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 condition occurs in most parts of the world, including Indonesia. The spread of this virus is very uncontrollable, WHO also declared this condition as a pandemic or an epidemic. WHO asks governments around the world to carry out early detection, including in Indonesia, this is done to reduce the spread rate and reduce the number of deaths due to COVID-19. On March 16, 2020 the central government of the Indonesian state decided to carry out self-quarantine in all parts of the country. This quarantine makes all community activities from children to parents carried out at home, including studying at home, working at home and worshipping at home. In Indonesia, the self-quarantine policy is called Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) which are regulated in Government Regulation No. 21/2020 concerning large-scale social savings in order to accelerate the handling of COVID-19, along with this, the Minister of Health Regulation No. 9/2020 on the trend for large-scale social.

The huge impact is felt by all citizens in various sectors starting from the health sector, the economic sector, the labor sector, the industrial sector and the education sector. Children from kindergarten to tertiary education cannot experience reading books in the library, bookstores, playing in the field, attending school and cannot play in the garden freely and freely like before COVID-19 arrived. Even starting from basic education, junior secondary education and senior secondary education no longer holding national exams as before, this is stated in a circular issued by the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 4 of 2020 concerning the implementation of education policies in the emergency period of the spread of COVID-19. Daniel (2020: 91) in his research revealed "The COVID-19 pandemic is a big challenge for the education system. This Viewpoint offers guidance for teachers, agency heads and officials in dealing with crises. In their small capacity to teach remotely, schools and colleges should take advantage of asynchronous learning, which works best in digital format". Daniel explained that currently the COVID-19 pandemic is such a challenge to the education system, this is what the closeness of the guidance for educators, heads of institutions and officials in

the education sector to share with this global crisis. The guide contains about increasing the capacity of educators in teaching the right distance from basic education to higher education by utilizing digital formats.

In Indonesia, data on student anxiety while studying at home due to COVID-19 is still very limited. Likewise with references that discuss related to students, knowing the root of the problem that occurs is very important to save students from anxiety, especially junior high school students. Providing self-efficacy materials is also important for them, teachers work together with counselors and psychologists to work together to provide self-efficacy materials to students to relieve anxiety in students during the COVID-19 pandemic.

1.1 PANDEMIC AGAINST STUDENTS

The condition of distant learning in total not only makes it difficult for educators and parents, but also makes it difficult for students. Students need to adjust to the various learning applications that are launched and used in their schools. In his research Baloran (2020: 638) explained that the COVID-19 pandemic conditions developed students' knowledge while studying at home, it was found that as many as 73.58% (390/530) of students saw that COVID-19 can spread through touching, sneezing, and food. The students also saw the main symptoms caused by COVID-19 infection, such as fever (517/530 or 97.55%). In addition, as many as 91.70% (486/530) students understood the importance of staying at home and carrying out study activities at home as a precaution for spreading the virus in the community. However, it is undeniable that this is also present in their minds during quarantine conditions, this makes as many as 62.64% (332/530) of students worry about food, even 54% to 56% of students avoid social contact, large gatherings. and play because of the news of catching COVID-19. The various information developing in the community about COVID-19 seems to be of high development for many parties, including students studying at home. This is certainly a new burden for students besides they have to keep achieving and have good relationships with friends and teachers, they also help adjust to the conditions of the pandemic that is happening.

Meanwhile, Hannela et al, (2020: 352) explain the pandemic of controversy which makes some students lose motivation, even the main challenge for teachers to students is less active interaction and spontaneity during teaching and learning. Teachers are also expected to be able to maximize the technology platform that is currently developing to maximize the teaching and learning process from home, to be able to prepare for future distance learning teachers must be given various trainings so that they can still motivate students to continue to excel.

1.2 MANAGE ANXIETY

Anxiety must be managed properly, the various impacts that arise if anxiety is not handled properly J. Mark (2003: 83) "Fear is an adaptive component of the acute" stress "response to potentially-dangerous (external and internal) stimuli which threaten to perturb homeostasis. However, when disproportional in intensity, chronic and / or irreversible, or not associated with any genuine risk, it may be symptomatic of a debilitating anxious state: for example, social phobia, panic attacks or generalized anxiety disorder. " In his research Mark explains that fear is an adaptive component of the stress response, but when the intensity is not chronic it may be a symptom of a debilitating anxious state: for example, social phobia, panic attacks or generalized anxiety disorder.

Linda and Devi (2017: 105) describe several physical symptoms of anxiety, such as: 1) restless behavior and difficulty sleeping; 2) muscles become tense in the shoulders, neck and abdomen; 3) changes in breathing rhythm; 4) chin, eyes and jaw contractions. Meanwhile, in psychic, among others: 1) difficulty to focus attention and concentration; 2) emotions undergo changes; 3) self-confidence has decreased; 4) very obsessed; 5) low self-motivation. It is feared that the students in school about the pandemic condition will have an impact on student learning outcomes, so it is necessary to take action to reduce this anxiety.

Various impacts will occur if students' anxiety is not handled immediately, in their research Irawan et al, (2020: 53) found 3 findings, namely: (1) students have started to get bored with online learning after the first two weeks of learning from home , (2) considerable anxiety on research subjects whose parents have low income, because they have to buy quotas to be able to participate in online learning, (3) mood or mood changes occur due to too many assignments and are considered effective by students. From these findings, it is necessary

for school psychologists and counselors to deal with problems that occur in students, in this case counselors and psychologists can provide self-efficacy material to students to be able to eliminate student anxiety. Research by Frank and M. Richard (1971: 498) explains the same thing due to anxiety by explaining "Anxiety management training (AMT) is a conditioning procedure to reduce anxiety reactions. AMT involves the arousal of anxiety and the training of the client to react to the anxiety with relaxation or success feelings. Unlike desensitization, AMT does not use anxiety hierarchies; it is based on the theory that anxiety responses can be discriminative stimuli, and that clients can be conditioned to respond to these cues with responses which remove these stimuli through reciprocal inhibition. " According to them, anxiety management training is a conditioning to reduce anxiety reactions. The client can be conditioned to respond to these cues with responses that eliminate these stimuli through reciprocal inhibition. Melda (2019: 179) reveals that self-efficacy in students must be built and grown, this will help motivate students to focus on achievement goals.

1.3 SELF EFFICACY

Bandura (2010: 3) explains that self-efficacy is defined as "Perceived self-efficacy is defined as people's beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives. Self-efficacy beliefs determine how people feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Such beliefs produce these diverse effects through four major processes. They include cognitive, motivational, affective and selection processes." Bandura explained that self-efficacy is a belief in how individuals feel, think, how to motivate themselves, and behave which of course will greatly affect the cognitive, motivation, affective and selection processes.

Frank (1996a: 544) discloses efficacy beliefs help determine how much effort people will expend on an activity, how long they will persevere when confronting obstacles, and how resilient they will prove in the face of adverse situations — the higher the sense of efficacy, the greater the effort, persistence, and resilience. Efficacy beliefs also influence individuals' thought patterns and emotional reactions. Self-efficacy in individuals will greatly help individuals to survive any problems faced. Frank (1996b: 86) also explains "found that students' mathematical self-efficacy beliefs were predictive of their choice of engaging in subtraction problems rather than in a different type of task: The higher the children's sense of efficacy, the greater their choice of the arithmetic activity. " That the effect of self-efficacy in mathematics, in particular, is needed to make it easier for students to choose activities in arithmetic activities.

1.4 ANXIETY AND SELF EFFICACY

Jennifer et al, (2013: 207) in their research found how self-efficacy in students was able to moderate student anxiety, especially when they were facing exams. Student self-efficacy has a very important role in building self-confidence in completing various tasks given by the teacher, even in all subjects in school.

Marisa et al, (2013: 1) found that poor self-efficacy will affect students' mathematics and science results, this is because negative self-confidence dominates in students and affects their self-confidence in completing exams.

II. METHOD

This research uses descriptive qualitative method. Sugiyono (2008: 9) explains that qualitative research itself is a research based on post-positivism philosophy, research is intended to examine natural objects, in this study experiment is the opposite and the researcher himself is the key instrument. Data collection techniques used are using primary data sources and secondary data sources. Primary data sources include questionnaires, observation, interviews, documentation. The informants of this study were mathematics teachers and school counseling teachers. Secondary sources are indirect sources that provide data to data collectors, for example through teachers in fields of study other than mathematics or in the form of documents.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 INITIAL CONDITIONS

Mutiara Baru Education Foundation is located in West Java, Indonesia, with educational levels starting from Kindergarten, Elementary School, Junior High School, Senior High School and Vocational High School.

The research was conducted at the Junior High School level in class IX of the 2019/2020 school year. Mutiara Baru Middle School has 39 teachers with various fields of study and there are 2 guidance and counseling teachers to handle students at the school. In accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 111 of 2014 concerning Guidance and Counseling in Primary and Secondary Education. Mutiara Baru School provides 2 hours of students each week so that guidance and counseling teachers can enter the classroom and provide guidance, counseling teachers at school also act as counselors who provide personal, learning, social and career services for students. So during the COVID-19 pandemic conditions, guidance and counseling teachers together with field teachers together help students reduce their learning anxiety.

3.2 QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

The results of observations made by researchers at Mutiara Junior High School found that there were 9 students who experienced very high anxiety compared to their peers. Based on the questionnaire questions given, the following questionnaire results were found:

TABLE 1. Questionnaire Assessment Score

Question Item Number	Score			
	4	3	2	1
1.	1	13	9	1
2.	9	12	1	2
3.	0	7	13	4
4.	3	16	4	1
5.	7	10	7	0
6.	7	11	5	1
7.	2	15	6	1
8.	4	11	7	2
9.	7	12	3	1
10.	8	16	0	0
11.	0	11	10	3
12.	3	11	8	2
13.	7	12	3	2
14.	5	15	3	1
15.	8	14	2	0
16.	4	16	4	0
17.	4	15	4	1
18.	7	12	3	2
19.	9	8	6	1
20.	5	14	5	0
21.	2	14	6	2
22.	2	15	4	2
23.	10	12	2	0

24.	7	11	5	1
25.	7	11	6	0
26.	6	6	10	2
27.	0	12	12	0
28.	5	15	4	0
29.	6	11	5	2
30.	5	12	5	2
31.	10	14	0	0
32.	6	12	5	0
33.	9	11	2	2
34.	6	11	7	0
35.	3	12	9	0
36.	6	11	8	0
37.	7	14	3	0
38.	8	11	5	0
39.	4	17	3	0
40.	12	12	0	0
41.	11	9	4	0
42.	12	8	4	0
43.	5	7	8	3
44.	6	8	4	5
45.	5	12	5	2

All questionnaire questions given to students are positive questions. The lower the value given by students, the lower the self-confidence and efficacy that students have. Through the dimensions of belief and generality, it was found that the results of students' self-confidence in the school were low on average, and the students' ability to cope with disappointment was also low. This data is supported by a list of values and conducting individual counseling regarding their self-efficacy and anxiety in mathematics.

3.3 Guidance and Counseling Teacher in Self Efficacy

Some of the actions given by the counseling guidance teacher to students in order to build self-efficacy are by providing material on understanding self-efficacy and its benefits for students. Self-efficacy material is given by the guidance and counseling teacher 2 times a week, after the teacher provides a report on learning outcomes in semester 1, the guidance and counseling teacher reveals "Self-efficacy needs to be given considering that mathematics cannot be avoided at all levels of education. Students must have high self-confidence, even though their numeracy skills are lower than other abilities in themselves. "

TABLE 2. List Of Final Exam Scores For Semester I
 Academic Year 2019/2020 Class VII
 Standard Value = 80

No	Name	Knowledge		Attitude
		Score	Result	
1.	BA	36	D	C

2.	KD	93	A	B
3.	MJ	78	C	B
4.	R	78	C	B
5.	GK	90	B	B
6.	FH	27	D	B
7.	KL	25	D	B
8.	YN	31	D	C
9.	RS	97	A	B
10.	ML	43	D	B
11.	JG	47	D	B
12.	YS	94	A	B
13.	JN	37	D	C
14.	TS	78	C	B
15.	RR	78	C	B
16.	J	80	C	B
17.	RW	78	C	B
18.	P	35	D	B
19.	Y	78	C	B

After receiving self-efficacy material for 2 hours a week by guidance and counseling teachers and mathematics teachers, results were found

TABLE 3. List Of Middle Exam Scores For Semester II
 Academic Year 2019/2020 Class VII
 Standard Value = 80

No	Name	Knowledge		Attitude
		Score	Result	
1.	BA	40	D	B
2.	KD	90	A	A
3.	MJ	80	C	B
4.	R	76	C	B
5.	GK	90	B	A
6.	FH	35	D	B
7.	KL	34	D	B
8.	YN	32	D	B
9.	RS	98	A	B
10.	ML	45	D	B
11.	JG	45	D	B
12.	YS	95	A	B
13.	JN	39	D	B
14.	TS	75	C	B
15.	RR	79	C	B
16.	J	83	C	B

17.	RW	80	C	A
18.	P	40	D	B
19.	Y	80	C	B

IV. CONCLUSION

The results showed that students' self-efficacy towards school subjects during a pandemic, especially mathematics, after receiving self-efficacy measures, experienced an increase in their self-confidence from before receiving self-efficacy measures. Self-efficacy towards students is a belief that students have in their ability to complete tasks, especially mathematics, both at home and at school. High anxiety towards all subjects during the COVID-19 pandemic makes students lose self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is very important for students, especially to relieve anxiety and generate achievement motivation in subjects including mathematics. The effect of this self-efficacy was measured from the final score of the semester 1 exam and class IX mid-semester test 2.

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